

VAKA TAKDİMİ

CASE REPORT

PNEUMOMEDIASTINUM WITHOUT PNEUMOTHORAX IN HUNGTINTON'S DISEASE: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

The presence of free air in the mediastinum for no apparent reason is defined as spontaneous pneumomediastinum (SPM). Huntington's Disease is a rare genetic disease. It is associated with progressive neurological dysfunctions. Nutritional deficiencies are likely to occur with the course of the disease. Alveolar wall weakness caused by nutritional deficiencies may be associated with spontaneous pneumomediastinum.

CASE

A 52-year-old female patient who was diagnosed with Huntington's disease 9 years ago presented to the emergency department with shortness of breath and decreased eating and drinking. SPM was detected in the patient who was taken to the intensive care unit with the diagnosis of aspiration pneumonia. We evaluated the patient's medical process.

Conclusion

Nutritional deficiency in Huntington's disease can be considered a risk factor for spontaneous pneumomediastinum

Key Words: *Progressive neurological dysfunctions, nutritional deficiencies, spontaneous pneumomediastinum, rare genetic disease*

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INTRODUCTION

Huntington's disease (HD) is a rare, hereditary, neurodegenerative disorder that causes progressive motor defects, psychiatric symptoms and cognitive impairment(1) The most typical finding is chorea, which gradually spreads to all muscles. Psychomotor processes are severely regressed. Unwanted weight loss, sleep and circadian rhythm disturbances, and autonomic nervous system dysfunction are common findings. The mean age of onset is between 30 and 50 years. The average duration of the disease is 17-20 years. The progression of the disease leads to greater dependence on everyday life and eventually to death. The most common cause of death is pneumonia, followed by suicide (1).

The presence of free air in the mediastinum that is not associated with trauma is known as spontaneous pneumomediastinum (SPM). It is a rare, self-limiting condition that can cause diffuse subcutaneous emphysema (2) Excessive coughing, recurrent attacks of increased abdominal pressure, vomiting or sneezing are considered risk factors for SPM.

We present a 52-year-old patient with spontaneous pneumomediastinum with Huntington's chorea.

CASE REPORT

A 52-year-old female patient was admitted to the emergency department with complaints of decreased eating and drinking, confusion and difficulty breathing. Hasta was taken to the intensive care unit for follow-up and treatment. It was learned that she has diagnosed with HD at the age of 42. The mother and her older sister have HD in the family history. She has three children, and 36-year-old children have HD. In the emergency department, Wbc:18.830, Hb:11,2, Plt:161000, Procalcitonin:100, Neu:17520, Lypn:950, Monocyte:110, Glucose:159, Creatine:2,16, Albumin:18,7, GFR:25,7, CRP:289,5, Na:156, K:5,13, AST:54, ALT:39, Ca:7,39, P:3,19, Ph:7,51, PCO₂: 29,6, PO₂: 164,7, INR:1,33, It came in as APTT:35.1, PT:12.3. On physical examination, it was observed that the patient was weak, his motor skills decrease, and he did not respond to verbal commands. There was no severe cough. It was stated by his relatives that he did not experience a severe cough until the hospital process. The level of consciousness was considered to be prone to sleep and confusion. The patient had pulse pressures that required inotropic treatment. The patient was provided with appropriate antibiotic therapy and hydration. Nasogastric tube feeding was started. The patient was followed up with nasal oxygen therapy on the first day of hospitalization. On the Computer Tomography (CT) image taken, free air around the aorta was noticed. (Figure 1). Pneumomediastinum was followed-up. The patient had no chest pain, and difficulty in swallowing was a complaint of the patient for a long-time swallowing difficulty could not be assessed because he did not take it orally after hospitalization. Hoarseness could not be assessed because he did not speak. Diffuse infiltration in the lung was interpreted in favor of aspiration pneumonia because it was more pronounced on the right side. Pneumothorax was not detected

(Figure 2). Similar to Covid 19 pneumonia, the radiological appearance was found to be cold in the differential diagnosis. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) came in negative. At the end of 48 hours, the patient was intubated on the development of signs of respiratory failure. On the second day of intubation, the patient showed signs of subcutaneous emphysema. On the left side of his chest, more pronounced dense subcutaneous emphysema was seen. Left hemithorax crepitations (Hamman's crunch) were released simultaneously with the heartbeat. The subcutaneous emphysema was masked in the following hours. The subcutaneous catheter was applied bilaterally to the patient. Within a period of 12 hours, the symptoms of subcutaneous emphysema regressed. A decrease in the need for inotropic therapy and an improvement in oxygen saturation were observed. Despite the increase in inotropic support given on the 7th day of hospitalization in the patient, a decrease in pulse pressure and a sudden rhythm of pulse loss were observed. He did not respond to cardiopulmonary resuscitation. The patient's death was accepted.

Figure 1. CT image. Free air around the aorta is marked with an arrow.

Figure 2. Direct chest radiography of subcutaneous emphysema.

DISCUSSION

We evaluated a case of spontaneous pneumomediastinum without pneumothorax, a rare clinical condition for HD, which is considered among the Rare Diseases. To the best of our knowledge, we present the first case of pneumomediastinum without pneumothorax reported among patients who were followed up with the diagnosis of HD.

Respiratory diseases have been reported as the most common cause of sudden death from Huntington's disease(3) Our patient suffered from a severe lower respiratory tract infection. We predicted aspiration-related lower respiratory tract infection due to existing swallowing difficulties and cooperating disorder and determined our treatment accordingly. Despite the insertion of a subcutaneous catheter for appropriate antibiotic therapy, nutrition, hydration and developing pneumomediastinum, patient death occurred.

There was no severe cough in our patient. Despite pneumonia, we attribute the absence of cough in the story to diminishing reflexes. We think that the cause of SPM in our patient may be alveolar wall damage due to long-term lack of feeding.

The presence of free air in the mediastinum without apparent cause is defined as SPM. The most common causes of SPM are gagging, vomiting, acute asthma attack, intense sports activity, drug inhalation, and weight loss(4)

In an animal study, it was reported that some lung tissues could be spent because the oxygen consumption of the organism and the lung decreased during the restriction of calories (5).

A Dutch study reported that improved health conditions and health care, leading to a prolongation of life expectancy in the general population, did not benefit individuals with Huntington's disease(5) However, knowing the medical conditions that can be investigated can contribute to changing the sudden death rates.

We believe that studies and case report evaluating the age and causes of death associated with Huntington's disease will increase awareness of the disease and have an impact on health policy indicators.

Disclaimer: The opinions expressed in the article belong to the authors. There is no official responsibility of any institution or financial source.

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding this manuscript.

REFERENCES

1. Roos RA. Huntington's disease: a clinical review. *Orphanet J Rare Dis.* 20 Aralık 2010;5:40.
2. Meireles J, Neves S, Castro A, França M. Spontaneous pneumomediastinum revisited. *Respir Med CME.* 01 Ocak 2011;4(4):181-3.
3. Solberg OK, Filkuková P, Frich JC, Feragen KJB. Age at Death and Causes of Death in Patients with Huntington Disease in Norway in 1986–2015. *J Huntingt Dis.* 01 Ocak 2018;7(1):77-86.
4. Devaraj U, Ramachandran P, D'souza GA. Recurrent spontaneous pneumomediastinum in a young female: Hamman's crunch revisited. *Oxf Med Case Rep.* 01 Mayıs 2014;2014(2):18-20.
5. Hille ETM, Siesling S, Vlis MV van der, Vandenbroucke JP, Roos RAC, Rosendaal FR. Two Centuries of Mortality in Ten Large Families with Huntington Disease: A Rising Impact of Gene Carriership. *Epidemiology.* 1999;10(6):706-10.